

STUDY PROTOCOL – 2022.11.20.

Title

Blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm: a systematic review and meta-analysis of case reports and individual records of patients

Registration Information

The study protocol will be uploaded to zenodo.org.

Authors

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Support

The study is supported by the Hungarian Society of Haematology and Transfusion. This research is not a company-initiated study. The funder of the study had no role in study design and will have no role in data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or the writing of the report.

Introduction

Condition being studied

Blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm (BPDCN) is a rare, but highly aggressive hematologic malignancy derived from plasmacytoid dendritic cells.

Objectives

We aim to collect and systematize the currently available evidence about the clinical presentation (age, gender, affected organs etc.) and genetics of BPDCN.

Review question 1: What are the main clinical characteristics of BPDCN?

In recent years as new drugs have been developed that could be effective at treating this disease, we aim to collect and systematize the currently available evidence about the treatment of BPDCN.

Review question 2: How do we treat BPDCN?

We aim to collect and systematize the currently available evidence about the immunohistochemical (IHC) and flow cytometric (FCM) data in the diagnosis of BPDCN.

Review question 3: In what percentage of cases are the investigated cell surface markers expressed in BPDCN?

The PICO formula for our review questions is not applicable.

Methods

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- *patient-level data on the following parameters regarding at least one patient: [1] CD4, CD56, and CD123 expression assessed either by immunohistochemistry (IHC) or flow cytometry (FCM); [2] age; [3] gender*
- *full-text publication is available*

Exclusion criteria:

- *patient-level data is not reported*
- *CD4, CD56 or CD123 negativity*
- *full-text publication is not available (e.g. conference abstract)*
- *the publication does not contain original data of at least one BPDCN patient (e.g. review, study protocol)*

Information Sources

A systematic search will be carried out in MEDLINE (via PubMed), Embase, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, Scopus, Web of Science, China National Knowledge Infrastructure, and Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature databases.

Detailed Search Strategy

MEDLINE (via PubMed)	
Date of search	2022.11.11.
Field of search	All Fields
Filters and restrictions	no
Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+/CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Translation	("blastic"[All Fields] AND ("dendritic cells"[MeSH Terms] OR ("dendritic"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields]) OR "dendritic cells"[All Fields] OR ("plasmacytoid"[All Fields] AND "dendritic"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "plasmacytoid dendritic cell"[All Fields]) AND ("neoplasm s"[All Fields] OR "neoplasms"[MeSH Terms] OR "neoplasms"[All Fields] OR "neoplasm"[All Fields])) OR "bpdcn"[All Fields] OR (("cutaneous"[All Fields] OR "cutaneously"[All Fields] OR "cutanous"[All Fields]) AND "agranular"[All Fields] AND "cd2"[All Fields] AND "cd4"[All Fields] AND ("cd56 antigen"[MeSH Terms] OR ("cd56"[All Fields] AND "antigen"[All Fields]) OR "cd56 antigen"[All Fields] OR "cd56"[All Fields]) AND ("lymphoma"[MeSH Terms] OR "lymphoma"[All Fields] OR "lymphomas"[All Fields] OR "lymphoma s"[All Fields])) OR ("agranular"[All Fields] AND "cd4"[All Fields] AND ("killer cells, natural"[MeSH Terms] OR ("killer"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields] AND "natural"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cells"[All Fields] OR ("natural"[All Fields] AND "killer"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cell"[All Fields]) AND ("leukaemia"[All Fields] OR "leukemia"[MeSH Terms] OR "leukemia"[All Fields] OR "leukaemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemia s"[All Fields])) OR ("agranular"[All Fields] AND "cd4"[All Fields] AND ("killer cells, natural"[MeSH Terms] OR ("killer"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields] AND "natural"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cells"[All Fields] OR ("nk"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "nk cell"[All Fields]) AND ("leukaemia"[All Fields] OR "leukemia"[MeSH Terms] OR "leukemia"[All Fields] OR "leukaemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemia s"[All Fields])) OR ("blastic"[All Fields] AND ("killer cells, natural"[MeSH Terms] OR ("killer"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields] AND "natural"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cells"[All Fields] OR ("nk"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "nk cell"[All Fields])

	<p>Fields]) AND ("leukaemia"[All Fields] OR "leukemia"[MeSH Terms] OR "leukemia"[All Fields] OR "leukaemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemia s"[All Fields])) OR ("blastic"[All Fields] AND ("killer cells, natural"[MeSH Terms] OR ("killer"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields] AND "natural"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cells"[All Fields] OR ("natural"[All Fields] AND "killer"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cell"[All Fields]) AND ("leukaemia"[All Fields] OR "leukemia"[MeSH Terms] OR "leukemia"[All Fields] OR "leukaemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemias"[All Fields] OR "leukemia s"[All Fields])) OR ("blastic"[All Fields] AND ("killer cells, natural"[MeSH Terms] OR ("killer"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields] AND "natural"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cells"[All Fields] OR ("nk"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "nk cell"[All Fields]) AND ("lymphoma"[MeSH Terms] OR "lymphoma"[All Fields] OR "lymphomas"[All Fields] OR "lymphoma s"[All Fields])) OR ("blastic"[All Fields] AND ("killer cells, natural"[MeSH Terms] OR ("killer"[All Fields] AND "cells"[All Fields] AND "natural"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cells"[All Fields] OR ("natural"[All Fields] AND "killer"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields]) OR "natural killer cell"[All Fields]) AND ("lymphoma"[MeSH Terms] OR "lymphoma"[All Fields] OR "lymphomas"[All Fields] OR "lymphoma s"[All Fields])) OR ("agranular"[All Fields] AND "cd4 cd56"[All Fields] AND "hematodermic"[All Fields] AND ("neoplasm s"[All Fields] OR "neoplasms"[MeSH Terms] OR "neoplasms"[All Fields] OR "neoplasm"[All Fields]))</p>
Number of records	761

Embase	
Date of search	2022.11.11
Field of search	All fields
Filters and restrictions	no
Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)

Translation	blastic AND plasmacytoid AND dendritic AND cell AND neoplasm OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous AND agranular AND cd2- AND cd4+ AND cd56+ AND lymphoma) OR (agranular AND cd4+ AND natural AND killer AND cell AND leukemia) OR (agranular AND cd4+ AND nk AND cell AND leukemia) OR (blastic AND nk AND cell AND leukemia) OR (blastic AND natural AND killer AND cell AND leukemia) OR (blastic AND nk AND cell AND lymphoma) OR (blastic AND natural AND killer AND cell AND lymphoma) OR (agranular AND cd4+ AND cd56+ AND hematodermic AND neoplasm)
Number of records	1344
Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL)	
Date of search	2022.11.11.
Field of search	All text
Filters and restrictions	no
Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Translation	blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm in All Text OR bpdcn in All Text OR cutaneous agranular CD2 CD4 CD56 lymphoma in All Text AND agranular CD4 natural killer cell leukemia in All Text AND (agranular CD4 NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4 CD56 hematodermic neoplasm) in All Text - (Word variations have been searched)
Number of records	10

Scopus	
Date of search	2022.11.11.
Field of search	All Fields
Filters and restrictions	no

Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Translation	ALL ((blastic AND plasmacytoid AND dendritic AND cell AND neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous AND agranular AND cd2- AND cd4+ AND cd56+ AND lymphoma) OR (agranular AND cd4+ AND natural AND killer AND cell AND leukemia) OR (agranular AND cd4+ AND nk AND cell AND leukemia) OR (blastic AND nk AND cell AND leukemia) OR (blastic AND natural AND killer AND cell AND leukemia) OR (blastic AND nk AND cell AND lymphoma) OR (blastic AND natural AND killer AND cell AND lymphoma) OR (agranular AND cd4+ AND cd56+ AND hematodermic AND neoplasm))
Number of records	3056

Web of Science	
Date of search	2022.11.11
Field of search	All fields
Filters and restrictions	no
Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+/CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Translation	ALL FIELDS: (blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR ALL FIELDS: (bpdcn) OR ALL FIELDS: (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR ALL FIELDS: (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR ALL FIELDS: (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR ALL FIELDS: (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR ALL FIELDS: (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR ALL FIELDS: (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR ALL FIELDS:

	(blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR ALL FIELDS: (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Number of records	865

LILACS, health information from Latin America and the Caribbean countries	
Date of search	2022.11.11.
Field of search	Title, abstract, subject
Filters and restrictions	no
Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Translation	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Number of records	18

CNKI (China National Knowledge Infrastructure, 中国知网)	
Date of search	2022.11.11.
Field of search	Theme, Title, Abstract, Full text, Summary, Keywords
Filters and restrictions	no
Search key	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural

	killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Translation	(blastic plasmacytoid dendritic cell neoplasm) OR bpdcn OR (cutaneous agranular CD2- CD4+ CD56+ lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ natural killer cell leukemia) OR (agranular CD4+ NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell leukemia) OR (blastic natural killer cell leukemia) OR (blastic NK cell lymphoma) OR (blastic natural killer cell lymphoma) OR (agranular CD4+ CD56+ hematodermic neoplasm)
Number of records	146

Study Selection Process

Records will be screened based on title, abstract, and full-text. The selection process will be conducted by two independent review authors. Disagreements will be resolved by an independent third investigator.

Data Extraction & Management

Based on the consensus of methodological and clinical experts, we will create a standardized data collection sheet. The following data will be extracted from each eligible article: study name, first author, publication year, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), country, gender, age, affected organs, treatment, overall survival, genetics (FISH, karyotype), and the expression of the below-listed proteins. Data will be extracted by two independent review authors using the standardized data collection form. Disagreements will be resolved by an independent third investigator.

AE1/AE3; alfa-1 antichymotrypsin; bcl2; bcl6; calponin; CD1a; CD2; CD2AP; CD3; CD3 alfa-beta (TCR alfa-beta); CD4; CD5; CD7; CD8; CD10; CD11b; CD11c; CD13; CD14; CD15; CD16; CD19; CD20; CD21; CD22; CD23; CD24; CD25; CD30; CD31; CD33; CD34; CD36; CD38; CD41; CD41a; CD43; CD45 (LCA); CD45RA; CD45RO; CD56; CD57; CD61; CD64; CD67; CD68 (PGM1/Phosphoglucomutase 1); CD71; CD74; CD79; CD79a, CD85g (ILT7, LIRA4); CD85k; CD99; CD117 (C-KIT); CD123; CD138; CD163; CD228 (EMA/epithelial membrane antigen/MUC1); CD234(Duffy Antigen Receptor for Chemokines/DARC); CD235a (glycophorin a); CD246 (Anaplastic lymphoma kinase/ALK); CD274 (Programmed death-ligand 1/PD-L1); CD279 (Programmed Death 1/PD-1); CD303 (blood dendritic cell antigen 2/BDCA2); CD304 (neuropilin-1/BDCA-4/VEGF165R); CgA (chromogranin A); CK5/6; CKP; cyclinD1; desmin; EBER (EBV encoded sRNA, LMP - latent membrane protein); F8; FMC7 (late B lymphocyte marker); granzymeB; HLADR; HMB-45 (human melanoma black 45); kappa:lambda light chains; Ki67 (positivity and %); lysozyme (muramidase); MELAN-A (MART-1); MPO (myeloperoxidase); MUM-1 (multiple myeloma oncogene 1); MX-1; myogenin; NG2 (neuron glial antigen2); non-specific esterase; NSE (neuron-specific enolase); Oct-4 (Octamer Transcription Factor 4); p63; pan-cytokeratin; PAX5 (paired box 5); PCMI (pericentriolar material1); perforin; S-100; Sal-like 4;

SMA; SYN (synaptophysin); TCF (T-cell factor); TCL1; TIA1; TdT (terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase); TIAL1; p-53; vimentin; WT-1 (Wilms' tumour-1);

Risk of Bias assessment

The Joanna Briggs Critical Appraisal Tools will be applied by two independent review authors. Disagreements will be resolved by an independent third investigator.

Data Synthesis

Data quality table will be created to report on the amount of missing information regarding all collected data. We intend to report on the ratio of positivity of each marker. We will summarize our findings in the form of tables and narratively. Other data will be analyzed descriptively (e.g. median+range regarding age, % of female patients).